

Development of auditory skills in infants

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Abstract:

Speech development is mixture of nature and nurture. Speech and language are an essential part of any child's development. Language development impacts the child's social interactions, behavior and academic skills. The first signs of communication occur when an infant learns that a cry will bring food, comfort, and companionship. Infant's communication skills grow dramatically in their first year of life. They learn how to express themselves, respond to parents or caretakers and understand when they try to communicate with them. Early detection of speech delays requires knowledge of speech and language milestones and recognition of high-risk indicators for disorders. The primary aim of early intervention in children with hearing impairment is to restore or promote the child's communication skills and to optimize the level of language development which impacts the cognitive and socioemotional behavior. Hearing screening programs in newborns enable detection of hearing impairment in the first few days after birth. Early identification and intervention with hearing augmentation within six months of age yields optimal effect. If undetected and without treatment, significant hearing impairment may negatively impact speech development and lead to disorders in psychological and mental behaviors. Infants who fail in hearing screening at hospital are referred for a repeat testing between two and eight weeks after discharge (second stage) and are examined by means of Oto acoustic emissions (OAE) followed by Automated Auditory Brainstem Response (ABR). Positive second stage results should be validated by otologic and audiological consultation. Comprehensive electrophysiological assessment includes diagnostic ABR testing and Auditory steady state response (ASSR) which are performed by audiologist. Finally, infants who are identified with a hearing loss should receive appropriate early stage intervention very soon after the final diagnosis is made and before six months of age. (287 words).

Keyword:

Auditory, Assessment, Audiometry, Auditory Brainstem Response (ABR), Otoacoustic Emissions (OAE).

References:

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Biography:

Dr. Debashis Acharya is passionate about Otorhinolaryngology (E.N.T.), being more than 27 years in the field including his training period from the prestigious Army Hospital (Research & Referral) affiliated to the University of Delhi, India. An ex- Indian Army Medical Corps officer (Lieutenant Colonel) served as E.N.T. Specialist in the Armed forces for approx. 12 years until 2008 when he left the services. He has worked as Medical Superintendent at a private Medical College Hospital in Western India after that for almost one year. He also holds a Masters degree in Hospital Administration from the International Symbiosis University, Pune, India. Subsequently held the appointment of H.O.D. & Associate Professor at Ahmedabad, India. for approx. two years before moving to Qatar in 2011. Presently working as Consultant E.N.T. in PHCC (Primary Health Care Corporation) --Govt. of QATAR since 2014. His academic articles have been published in various foreign E.N.T. journals and he is also Honorary Editor of many such publications. He has been an Organizing Committee member & Chairman of various international E.N.T. conferences across the Gulf region, India, U.K., Singapore & Italy to mention a few. His special interest areas are Audiovestibular Medicine & Rhinology.